

Impact of Digital Marketing on Consumer Buying Behavior- A Study from a Metropolitan City Karachi

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Abstract:

Digital marketing is one of the most cost effective and measurable methods used by small businesses and multinationals, to track, monitor and target their audience's preferences through Digital Marketing platforms like social media marketing, Email marketing and mobile marketing by running different campaigns (example: Awareness, consideration and conversion) accordingly to get the best results. The study investigates the impact of digital marketing towards consumer buying intention in pakistani context (Textile industry). This research will be focussing on how digitalization has changed how we associate with firms, items and brands through online administrations by putting away, examining and playing amusement, email, Facebook and other such applications. The techniques which will be used to measure the impact of digital marketing towards consumer buying intention are descriptive statistics, correlation and regression. The results show that social media marketing, email marketing and mobile marketing has a significant affect on consumer buying intention with social media marketing having the greatest affect on consumer buying intention. The study concludes and confirms that email marketing and mobile marketing have a significant impact on consumer buying intention.

Keywords: Online Behavior, Buying intention, Social Media Marketing, Email Marketing, Mobile Marketing

Introduction

The focus of the study investigators was on the digital aspect of marketing rather than the practice of innovative advancements, which included observing and analyzing customer response, the reaction to client input, the progressive implementation plan, the establishment of advanced administration reputations, the investigation of online media's effect, and the combination of outsider survey destinations that all strive to improve execution (Pelsmacker, Van Tilburg, & Holthof, 2018). Traditional marketing strategies are being impacted by the rise of technology-based digital publicity, which necessitates rethinking in order to stay relevant in an advanced age. Content marketing was formerly thought to be the key to successful internet marketing operations and a tool for advanced advertising. Based on a meeting research of 262 advertising heads towards digital advertising doings that lead to a growth in financial plan in the coming years, the online study was directed to pick the final fate of advanced advertising (Baltes, 2015).

Many big brands like Coca-Cola, Pepsi, the New York Times, Adidas and Nike, among other well-known businesses, have recently adopted digitalized marketing operations. Because of its crucial importance, DMC has been found to be effective in creating and fostering buyer attention. The influence of digital content promotion has been shown on employee dedication, deal expansion, as well as trust and loyalty (Hollebeek & Macky, 2019).

The rise of intent innovation has had an impact on innovation-based commercial activities, such as advertising, and has sparked a lot of thought because of its importance in today's corporate. Because of its wide reach, electronic advertising allows businesses to reach a large number of customers. Because of the altered way of life of customers and their buying preferences, web-based apps have modified the standards of advertising, which have been re-imagined. Because of the idea of innovation and digitalization as more established instances are not suited for the economic advancement of companies, traditional advertising processes have been modified. Advanced marketing is seen to be essential for businesses to direct business at a serious level in today's rapidly changing environment. Digitalization centralizes the technique of communication and data exchange among company stakeholders, allowing for boost revenue and the establishment of long-distance connections (Batinic, 2015).

Previous research has also discovered a link between audits and purchase goals in the hotel industry, which is related to room occupancy. The tests have revealed that the number of audits has a significant influence on the occupancy rate, regardless of survey ratings. Investigations have revealed that the number of online audits has a significant impact on the exhibition. Negative audits show how popular an item or administration is, and it draws attention to it. The large number of surveys keeps the item in the client's mind for a long time and attracts data seekers by reducing insecurity and risk. This has a significant influence on clients' practices. On the basis of their findings, the studies concluded that notoriety has a significant role in buyer preferences. Better audits, according to the study's findings, influence the exhibition and the buying behavior of clients in the neighborliness industry (De Pelsmacker, Van Tilburg, & Holthof, 2018).

According to a study conducted by (Hurley, 2016), companies are increasingly focusing on the use of a tools which focus on retargeting to increase the range of their advertising. It focuses on individual clients who have recently visited the shop. Retargeting is a concept that uses assessment data to retarget consumers and engage with them in order to encourage them to make a purchase. Retargeting is a fundamental part of advertising tactics, according to (Singlegraincom, 2017). It's crucial for showing and building trust between the company and its customers. It makes use of information from customers who have already visited the establishment.

Background

Advertising is a dynamic, energetic, and engaged commercial endeavour. Because of changing economic conditions- material and energy shortages, monetary instabilities, high unemployment, passing on organisations, legal pressure effects due to fast innovative changes in specific businesses - the function of promotion has changed significantly (Bala, Verma, & D., 2018). Such changes, including the internet specially digital marketing have caused today's advertising chiefs to become more market oriented in their key dynamic, necessitating formal methods for gathering precise and correct information on customers, goods, the industry community, and the entire environment. The use of the Internet to shop for and sell products or services is known as net exhibiting. To trade and market goods, net displaying makes use of the electronic industry's power. Any online store qualifies as an electronic transaction. Selling, purchasing, and exchanging of items or organisations through the internet is the responsibility of the electronic corporation. Internet or digital world advancing is a subset of the electronic industry. With the advancement of the internet, online displaying has become increasingly popular. It is thought that Internet advancement began in the early 1990s with the advancement of the internet; it is no longer just about selling goods on your own, but also about adding information space, programming plans, deals, stock exchange, and matching (Bala, Verma, & D., 2018).

According to Chaffey, 2011 social media marketing include "stimulating buyer communications on the company's own website or through social media." Firms may utilise social network formulas to assign their messages to their target viewers without giving for the editors or wholesalers, which is typical of old-style advertising. In the digital era, the most prevalent formulas are social media advertising and email marketing. Get Response's investigation revealed that email marketing is the most sophisticated marketing approach. Clients who are interested in special offers are targeted through email advertising. Buyers who agree to receive email advertising are more likely to make a purchase. Client loyalty is also influenced by social media marketing (Putter, 2017). The evolution of social media has benefited both traditional and promotional contact.

These new specialised gadgets enable customers to participate in the correspondence cycle by glancing at the distant section in traditional correspondence. Online media platforms that enable two-way communication between customers and companies have grown in popularity (Berthon et al., 2008).

Online Behavior theory

It suggests that people prefer to shop for daily necessities online rather than going out, and that as a result, local markets are declining. To save time and get some rest instead of squandering the day at local markets, the working class chooses to buy groceries and clothing online. Over time, consumer sentiments have shifted. People are beginning to trust internet buying more than local marketplaces since they can readily obtain branded things. Life has become easier as a result of online buying (Hanekom & Barker, 2016).

Consumer buying intention

Customers demonstrate their likelihood, capacity, or plan to buy particular brands through buy goal (Mirabi, Akbariyeh, & Tahmasebifard, 2015). Buy expectation is defined as a part of a buyer's behaviour, such as their attitude toward certain products or services (Soebagyo, 2014). A few suggestions, (Putri, 2017) may be able to recognise it as: Transactional: A person's desire to purchase the item or service being offered. Refractive: A person's proclivity to discuss things or services with others. Special: A passion that distinguishes someone who has a strong preference for one thing or service over another. If something goes wrong with the goods or service, this feeling must be expressed. Explorative: An interest that describes the pursuit of information about a product or service that a person is interested in.

As per (Mihart 2012) studies finding the dynamic are the social comprehension towards the acquisition of the object, as described by the customer lead. He referred to the customer as the "difficult solver." Clients demand time and consideration when it comes to the products that they decide to buy based on their decision and goal. Aside from that, the creator revealed the three-level influence on the buyer's dynamic.

One of the studies led by (Malik, et al., 2013) discussed the role of the brand image and the promoting strategy in the formation of shopper purchasing behaviour. Their goal was to determine how the brand image that was promoted influenced their behaviour toward purchasing expectations. Furthermore, the study discovered that females' purchasing behaviour is more secure since they are the ones who are drawn in by the brand, their own self-image about the brand, and a different emotion. The term "buy expectation" refers to what a buyer believes or contemplates purchasing (Blackwell, Miniard, & Engel, 2001). Customers' favourable or negative attitudes and beliefs about a brand and purchase goal in an electronic environment, such as web-based media, are based on the results of negative and positive online surveys of that brand (Lee, Park, & Han, 2008). (Udeledu, 2017) defines customer buying behaviour as "the buyer's buying expectation that a corporation must analyse before marketing the goods." The buyer's reaction has an influence on the marketing strategy used by businesses to gain astonishing and horrible ground.

Social Media Marketing (SMM)

A more common issue on social networking Facebook has made it possible for organisations to communicate with a big number of people about things and welfares, as well as for fresh advancing beginnings to keep an eye on them. This is only compelling if the leaders are fully aware of the need of consuming communication philosophies in order to appeal to clients and improve their expertise (Mangold, Glynn, & David, 2009). Online social proceeding actions and plans should be accurately measured, and implementation assessment points should be used to learn how to do so. As market forces shift throughout the world in relation to young people's receptivity to and use of electronic media, important joining strategies must be included in the organization's ongoing communication plan. Administrations gears have a greater influence than regular communication programs (Helm, Moller, Mauroner, & Caonard, 2013). Client understanding increases in confidence and fulfilment when they adj0075st access online media, which is itself a driving sign for associations and developing proficiently as a segment of learning (Pai & Arnott, 2013). Clients' psychological patterns are

influenced by their online shopping experiences, which improves their purchase decisions (Cetina, Cristiana, & Raduledcu, 2012).

Research findings demonstrated the positive impact of internet advertising on the purchase objective (Husnain & Toor, 2017). Web-based media advertising has been shown to influence purchase intent through online conversation like E-WOM or feedbacks (Rudyanto, 2018). Shoppers gain intuitive information from both familiar and novel groups via web-based media. The preceding discussions led to the conclusion that web-based media has a significant influence on consumer purchase expectations and intentions.

Email Marketing

When a customer sees an item on the internet or receives an item offer through email, buy objectives are set off replicating them in order to do market research and further investigation. As a potential becomes satisfied with the indexed listings, he eventually settles on the buy option and purchases the item. Currently, if marketers take the assurance and value that they guaranteed in their promotion, customers will offer excessive audits; nevertheless, if the assurance isn't visible, customers will give poor audits, and the chances of up-selling or repaying are nearly impossible. This is accomplished using a comparable medium, namely the internet (Castronovo & Huang, 2012). In his judgement of the buyer's purchasing point, which is influenced by the decisions of other people? The acquisition of a buddy is crucial to the purchase decision, and the allotted correspondence anticipates a vital role in it. Online media platforms that combine email showcasing and other web expanding methods are now used to complete the discourse. Buyers are now completely reliant on the opinions of others, as expressed through e-WOM and messaging.

Email marketing is a specialised tool that involves sending messages to individuals or groups of people via email (GhavamiLahiji, 2016). Email marketing enables the advertisers the exchange of ads, organisation solicitations or presents, and other messages in order increase range of brand awareness. Email marketing is a highly responsive tool for quickly accomplishing tasks and establishing customer relationships (Ali, et al., 2015).

Mobile Marketing

It's a way for dealing with lead information on goods and companies via mobile and portable plans. Link can direct information as text (SMS), graphics, video, or music utilising mobile devices (MMS). During the 2000s, marketing by mobile SMS (Short Message Service) became more popular in Europe and a few parts of Asia. Demand insistences can be guided by employing message to send out alarms. Using the messaging strategy for campaigns yields more immediate and meaningful outcomes. Associations may use this strategy to present publicising messages to their clients rationally, at any time, and be confident that the material will be understood. Associations might conduct a survey and obtain extensive client analysis data in order to expand their businesses or organisations in the future (Yasmin, Tasneem, & Fatema, 2015).

According to research conducted by (Rohm, Gao, & Pagani, 2012), one of the quickest growing advancements in publicising is simple progressing. Their research found that communication via flexible displaying has evolved into something more commonplace as a result of the widespread adoption of mobile phones. Because convenient exhibiting should not be connected to the work area or PCs, the remote aspect of flexible correspondence gradually converts into an example, as people have recognised it as helpful to utilise. Furthermore, their analysis reveals that purchasers in the United States of America are generally powerful and use their mobile phones to reach the business.

Problem statement

Previous studies findings have focused on the importance of using web-based media and it is beneficial for the company (Siamagka, Christodoulides, Valvi, & Michaelidou, 2015). It has been concluded that over 70% of inhabitants of the United Arab Emirates (UAE) seek advice from social media before making a purchase, since social media programs are known to supply clients with data. Electronic commercial center development allows businesses to connect with a large number of customers via long-distance informal contact channels. Clients

may purchase online from any location using web-based media and sophisticated media technologies, eliminating the need for physical transportation. The usage of innovatively based apps and online media applications has grown in importance, and researches have given it greater attention due to its vital role in today's serious corporate environment (Gazal, Montague, Poudel, & Wiendenbeck, 2016). Because of the lack of traditional assets, various studies has shown that specially small and medium businesses (SMEs) can profit from the effective use of online media (Durkin, McGowan, & McKeown, 2013).

Especially after COVID online/social media marketing has emerged as a new advertising tool. The associations believe that using persuasive marketing strategies will increase the benefit. Furthermore, any company's most important goal is to increase efficiency and lower production costs. For marketing, each company uses different web-based media such as social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and other online media. As a result of 4G/5G managements, the web is in the entrance of an appealing individual who is using a mobile phone. As a result, the rapid expansion of the internet is a sign of using the internet as a marketing tool, as well as an appealing open door for any company to modify customer perceptions through social-based media advertising (Ali, Rauf, Shabbir, & Hussain, 2016).

Research Significance

This study is important to check the impact of performance marketing on consumer buying intentions in the Pakistani context (Textile industry), because nowadays every brand uses digital media platforms to continuously engage their audience, and even those who want to become brands in the future will use digital marketing tools such as mobile marketing, email marketing, social media platforms, and affiliate marketing to reach their target audience. This study will elaborate the impact of digital marketing on customer purchasing intentions. The research will also look at issues including changing customer attitudes through marketing and promotional initiatives, such as giving cheap pricing and discounts to encourage brand loyalty.

Research Hypothesis

H1: Social media marketing has a significant positive effect on consumer buying behavior.

H2: Mobile Marketing has a significant positive effect on consumer buying behavior.

H3: Email Marketing has a significant positive effect on consumer buying behavior.

Research Questions

Central Question

- To what extent Digital marketing affects Consumer buying behavior?

Sub-Questions

- To what extent social media marketing affects Consumer buying behavior?
- To what extent Mobile Marketing affects Consumer buying behavior?
- To what extent Email Marketing affects Consumer buying behavior?

Research Objective

- To ascertain the effect of overall Digital marketing (Social media marketing, Mobile marketing, Email marketing) on Consumer buying behavior.
- To find the most important variable or aspect of Digital marketing in context of consumer buying behavior.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Methodology

Research design

The convenience sampling technique will be employed in this study, and a sample size of 250 will be used to perform the study. Karachi residents are the intended audience. The majority of Karachi's youth like it since they use the internet more regularly. Individuals from various departments of the institution, as well as family members and friends, will be approached and requested to complete the surveys. A quantitative technique was used in this study, and the research design was based on causal and cross-sectional data, as well as hypothesis testing.

Research Approach

This research will be exploring the impact of digital marketing towards consumer buying intention in Pakistani context and a deductive approach and explanatory research will be used.

Study Instruments

In this study, a structured questionnaire was used as this study instrument, which was adapted from prior studies.

Data Collection and Statistical Techniques

We will collect primary data and data through questionnaires for this study. Quantitative research will be used in this project that is to determine the influence of customer purchasing intentions on digital marketing in the setting of Pakistan. The questionnaire will include questions on respondents and factors, and it will be designed on a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 representing strongly disagree, 2 representing disagree, 3 representing neutral, 4 representing agree and 5 representing strongly agree, using SPSS 20. The first section will have questions on respondent demographics, while the remaining sections will include questions about both the dependent and independent variables.

MLR- Multiple Linear Regression technique was used to find impact of independent variable on a dependent variable i.e. mobile marketing, email marketing, and social media marketing on consumer buying intention in Pakistani context using social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, and Pinterest. The importance of the hypothesis suggested in this study will be assessed using this survey. In this study, both Causal and Descriptive statistics were applied. SPSS was also used to do Cronbach's alpha and correlation tests.

Results and Discussion

Demographic analysis

Table 1
Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	94	41.2	41.2	41.2
	Female	134	58.8	58.8	100
	Total	228	100	100	

The gender distribution of the respondents who filled out this questionnaire and discovered that out of 228 replies, 134 were filled out by women, accounting for 58.8%, and 41.2 percent were filled out by men, accounting for 94 responses.

Table 2
Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Less than 21	30	13.2	13.2	13.2
	21 to 30	139	61	61	74.1
	31 to 40	54	23.7	23.7	97.8
	41 to 50	5	2.2	2.2	100
	Total	228	100	100	

The age level of respondents is defined by the above results: the majority of the samples were between the ages of 21 and 30, accounting for 61.0 percent of the total, while 54 out of 228 were between the ages of 31 and 40, accounting for 23.7 percent, 5 out of 228 were between the ages of 41 and 50, accounting for 2.2 percent, and 30 out of 228 were under the age of 21 years, accounting for 13.2 percent of the total.

Table 3

Education

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Intermediate/A level	57	25	25	25
	Undergraduate	4	1.8	1.8	26.8
	Graduate	113	49.6	49.6	76.3
	Masters	54	23.7	23.7	100
	Total	228	100	100	

The above results show that the majority of respondents had a graduate degree, with 113 out of 228 having a total percentage of 49.6%, 4 out of 228 having an undergraduate degree, with a total percentage of 1.8 percent,

57 out of 228 having an intermediate/a level, with a total percentage of 25.0 percent, and 54 out of 228 having a master's degree, with a total percentage of 23.7 percent, indicating that the majority of respondents were educated.

Table 4

Occupation

		occupation			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Employee	108	47.4	47.4	47.4
	Own Business	55	24.1	24.1	71.5
	Student	65	28.5	28.5	100
	Total	228	100	100	

The occupations of the respondents are defined by the above statistics; the majority of them were employees (108 out of 228 total), with a total percentage of 47.4 percent, while 55 out of 228 had their own business (24.1 percent), and 65 out of 228 were students (28.5 percent).

Table 5
Reliability Analysis

Variable	Cronbach alpha
Consumer Buying Intention	0.676
Social Media Marketing(IDV)	0.549
Email Marketing(IDV)	0.785
Mobile Marketing(IDV)	0.627
Overall Reliability	0.814

The instrument's overall dependability is 0.814, indicating that it is suitable for a variety of statistical studies. Furthermore, each construct's individual reliability is greater than 0.6, indicating that each construct is trustworthy for various statistical analyses.

Table 6
Correlations

Correlations

		CBI	SMM	EM	MM
CBI	Pearson Correlation	1	.537**	.285**	.379**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0	0	0
	N	228	228	228	228
SMM	Pearson Correlation	.537**	1	.260**	.392**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0		0	0
	N	228	228	228	228
EM	Pearson Correlation	.285**	.260**	1	.665**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0		0
	N	228	228	228	228
MM	Pearson Correlation	.379**	.392**	.665**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0	0	0	
	N	228	228	228	228

If you look at table 6 diagonally, the Pearson's correlation for each variable is 1. There is a perfect correlation between the variables. Consumer purchasing intent and social media marketing have a correlation value of 0.537. There are 228 respondents in the sample that answered both questions. This correlation coefficient has a P-value of 0.000. Because the P-value is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant association between Consumer purchase intention and Social media marketing. Consumer purchasing intent and email marketing have a correlation value of 0.285. There are 228 respondents in the sample that answered both questions. This correlation coefficient has a P-value of 0.000. Because the P-value is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant association between Consumer Buying Intention and Email Marketing. Consumer purchasing intent and mobile marketing have a correlation value of 0.379. There are 228 respondents in the sample that answered both questions. This correlation coefficient has a P-value of 0.000. Because the p-value is less than 0.05, there is a statistically significant association between Consumer purchase intention and Mobile marketing.

Table 7

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.569 ^a	0.324	0.315	0.37337	0.324	35.749	3	224	0

a. Predictors: (Constant), MM, SMM, EM

Table 4.3, explains the model that R is 56.9% which shows a positive relationship between the variables. Adjusted R Square shows .315, which means this model, is explaining 32.4% of the variance.

Table 4.8

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	14.951	3	4.984	35.749	.000 ^b
1	Residual	31.228	224	0.139		
	Total	46.179	227			

a. Dependent Variable: CBI

In Table 7, F value is 35.749 and Sig value is under 0.05 which shows model is fit and significant.

Table 8

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound
	(Constant)	1.031	0.27		3.819	0	0.499	1.563
1	SMM	0.526	0.068	0.459	7.684	0	0.391	0.661
	EM	0.047	0.059	0.059	0.803	0.423	-0.069	0.164
	MM	0.151	0.073	0.16	2.066	0.04	0.007	0.295

a. Dependent Variable: CBI

Table 8 demonstrates the regression analysis performed to assess the significance level, model fit, and impact of social media marketing (SMM), email marketing (EM), and mobile marketing (MM) on consumer purchasing intentions (CBI).

With t = 7.684 and sig = 0.000, the relationship between social media marketing and consumer buying intention (CBI) is negligible, indicating a positive but insignificant effect on CBI. The figure clearly illustrates that a 1%

change in social media marketing would result in a 52.6 percent change in consumer purchase intentions since the 0.526 coefficient change is perfectly related.

With $t = 0.803$ and $sig = 0.423$, the relationship between Email marketing and Consumer Buying Intention (CBI) is negligible, indicating a negative minor effect on CBI. The table plainly illustrates that a 1% change in Email marketing will result in a 4.7 percent change in Consumer Preferences since the 0.047 coefficient change is precisely related.

With $t = 2.066$ and $sig = 0.040$, the relationship between Mobile marketing and Consumer buying + (CBI) is negligible, indicating a positive but insignificant impact on Consumer buying intention. Because Mobile marketing is precisely related to 0.151 coefficient change, a 1% change in Mobile marketing will result in a 15.1 percent change in Consumer buying intention.

Table 9
Hypotheses Testing

S. No.	Hypotheses	Sig. Value	Empirical Conclusion
1	H1: Social media marketing has a significant positive impact on customer purchasing intention	0	Accepted
2	H2: Mobile Marketing has a significant positive impact on Customer Purchasing Intention	0.04	Accepted
3	H3: Email Marketing has a significant positive impact on Customer Purchasing Intention	0.423	Rejected

Conclusion

The goal of this study is to determine the impact of independent factors on dependent variables among respondents from Karachi, Pakistan, who used social media and undertook online textile shopping. We looked at the impact of independent factors on the dependent variable using regression and correlation in SPSS. According to the data of 228 respondents who bought things online, there is a substantial association between the independent and dependent variables.

Consumer purchasing intent is the most important component in producing revenue for a company. This research looked at how the parameters I employed in this study influenced purchasing intentions. We discovered that social media marketing is the driving force behind purchase intent. Consumers evaluate products on social media groups to share their experiences with them, and these reviews impact the purchasing decisions of new buyers. Customers will avoid considering a product or service if the reviews are bad. As a result, businesses must try to satisfy clients in order to receive good feedback on their products and services. When clients are pleased with an organization's efforts, they are ready to provide a positive review on social media platforms.

There are certain limitations to this study that may pave the way for future research. First, this research focuses on gathering data from students, primarily teenagers, who are interested in purchasing items online during a pandemic. Second, we only used a few variables, and there might be many more that influence customer purchasing intentions. Finally, the study's sample size is restricted to 228 people. Furthermore, data was obtained via closed-ended questions, which limited the scope of the research.

References

- Ali, M., U., Uddin, & M. (2016,2011). Consumers' Attitude towards Online Shopping: Factors influencing Gotland consumers to shop online.
- Ali, Z., Ejaz, S., Aleem, A., Saeed, M., M., U., Tahir, F. A., & Kashif, M. (2015). Understanding Emarketing as a Firm's Promotional tool and Its Impact on Consumer Perception. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 5(3), 365.
- Ali, Z., Shabbir, M. A., Rauf, M., & Hussain, A. (2016). To assess the impact of social media marketing on consumer perception. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 6(3), 69-77.
- Bala, M., Verma, & D. (2018). A critical review of digital marketing. *International Journal of Management, IT & Engineering*, 8(10), 321-339.
- Balance, T. (2016). *Why Email Marketing Is Still the Best Thing Since Sliced Bread for Business*. [online]. Retrieved from Available at: <https://www.thebalance.com/email-marketing-2948346>[Accessed 19 Nov. 2017].
- Baltes, L. P. (2015). Content marketing-the fundamental tool of digital marketing. *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov. Economic Sciences.*, 8(2), 111.
- Batinic, I. (2015). The role and importance of internet marketing in modern hotel industry. *Journal of Process Management. New Technologies*, 3(3), 34-38.
- Bismo, A., & Putter, S. (2019, August). Application of Digital Marketing (social media and email marketing) and its Impact on Customer Engagement in Purchase Intention: a case study at PT. *Soltius Indonesia*. In *2019 International Conference on Information Management and Technology (ICIMTech)*, 1, pp. 109-114.
- Blackwell, R. D., Miniard, P. W., & Engel, J. F. (2001). *Consumer Behavior*. New York: Harcourt College Publishers.
- Castronovo, C., & Huang, L. (2012). Social media in an alternative marketing communication model. *Journal of Marketing Development and Competitiveness*, 6(1), 117.
- Cetina, J., Cristiana, M., & Radulecu, V. (2012). "Psychological and Social Factors that Influence Online Consumer Behavior". *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 62, 184-188.
- Chaffey, D. (2011). *E-Business and E-Commerce Management: Strategy, Implementation, and Practice*.
- Chen, L. (2014). The influence of social media on consumer behavior: An empirical study on factors influencing consumer purchase intention in China under the social media context. AARHUS UNIVERSITY.
- De Pelsmacker, P., Van Tilburg, S., & Holthof, C. (2018). Digital marketing strategies, online reviews and hotel performance. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 72, 47-55.
- Durkin, M., McGowan, P., & McKeown, N. (2013). Exploring social media adoption in small to medium-sized enterprises in Ireland. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 20(4), 716-734.
- Gazal, K., Montague, I., Poudel, R., & Wiendenbeck, J. (2016). Forest products industry in a digital age: Factors affecting social media adoption. *Forest Products Journal*, 66(5), 343-353.
- GhavamiLahiji, S. (2016). The Effect of Email Marketing on Buyers' Behavior. *International Journal of Innovative and Applied Research*, 4(1), 77-80.
- Hanna, Rohm, & Crittenden. (2011). "We're all connected: The power of the social media ecosystem". *Business Horizons*, 54(3), 265-273.
- Helm, R., Moller, M., Mauroner, O., & Caonard, D. (2013). "The effects of a lack of social recognition on online communication behavior". *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29, 1065-1077.
- Hollebeek, L. D., & Macky, K. (2019). Digital content marketing's role in fostering consumer engagement, trust, and value: Framework, fundamental propositions, and implications. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 45, 27-41.

- Hurley, D. (2016). An Investigation of the Impact of Retargeting Mobile Advertising on Customer's Purchase Intentions—A Study of the Irish Millennial Market . *Doctora dissertation, Dublin Business*.
- Husnain, M., & Toor, A. (2017). The impact of social network marketing on consumer purchase intention in Pakistan: Consumer engagement as a mediator. *AJBA*, 10(1), 167-199.
- Katawetawaraks, C., & Wang, C. (2011). Online Shopper Behavior: Influences of Online Shopping Decision. *Asian Journal of Business Research*, 1(2).
- Keller, K. L. (1993). Conceptualizing, Measuring, and Managing Customer-Based Brand Equity. *Journal of Marketing*, 57(1), 1-22.
- Kili, C., Leu, D. J., Marttunen, M., Hautala, J., & Leppanen, P. H. (2019). This is an electronic reprint of the original.
- Kim, A. J., & Ko, E. (2010). Impacts Of Luxury Fashion Brand's Social Media Marketing On Customer Relationship And Purchase Intention. *Journal of Global Fashion Marketing*, 1(3), 164-171.
- Lee, J., Park, D. H., & Han, I. (2008). The Effect Of Negative Online Consumer Reviews On Product Attitude: An Information Processing View. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 7(3), 341-352.
- Malik, M. E., Ghafoor, M. M., Iqbal, H. K., Ali, Q., Hunbal, H., Noman, M., & Ahmad, B. (2013). Impact of brand image and advertisement on consumer buying behavior. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 23(1), 117-122.
- Mangold, Glynn, W., & David, J. F. (2009). "Social Media: The New Hybrid Element of the Promotion Mix." *Business Horizons*, 52, 357-365.
- Marketo.com. (2017, Nov 19). *What is Mobile Marketing? Overview & Resources*. [online]. Retrieved from Available at: <https://www.marketo.com/mobile-marketing/> [Accessed 19 Nov. 2017].
- Melian-Gonzalez, S., & Bulchand-Gidumal, J. (2016). A model that connects information technology and hotel performance. *Tourism management*, 53, 30-37.
- Merisavo, M., & R., M. (2004). The Impact of Email Marketing on Brand Loyalty. *Journal of Product and Brand Management*, 13(6), 498-505.
- Mihart, C. (2012). Impact of integrated marketing communication on consumer behaviour: effects on consumer decision-making process. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 4(2), 121.
- Mirabi, V., Akbariyeh, H., & Tahmasebifard, H. (2015). A study of factors affecting on customers purchase intention. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Engineering Science and Technology (JMEST)*, 2(1).
- Pai, P., & Arnott, D. (2013). "User adoption of social networking sites: Eliciting uses and gratification through a means-end approach". *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(3), 1039-1053.
- Putri, C. S. (2017). Pengaruh media sosial terhadap keputusan pembelian konsumen cherie melalui minat beli. *Performa*, 1(5), 594-603.
- Putter, M. (2017). The impact of social media on consumer buying intention. 3(1), 7-13.
- Reza, J. M., & Samiei, N. (2012). The Effect of Word of Mouth on Inbound Tourists' Decision for Traveling to Islamic Destinations (The Case of Isfahan as a Tourist Destination in Iran). *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 3(1), 12-21.
- Rohm, A. J., Gao, T. T., & Pagani, M. (2012). Brand in the hand: A cross-market investigation of consumer acceptance of mobile marketing. *Business Horizons*, 55(5), 485-493.
- Rudyanto, R. (2018). Pengaruh Pemasaran Jejaring Media Sosial Dan Keterkaitan Konsumen Terhadap Niat Beli Konsumen. *Journal Manajemen dan Pemasaran Jasa*, 11(2), 177-200.
- Samsudeen, S. N., & Kaldeen, M. (2020). Impact of digital marketing on purchase intention.
- Sethi, G., Singh, & I., M. (n.d.). The Impact of Mobile Advertisement on the Students of Manipur University.
- Sethi, G., Singh, I., Khan, I., . . . F. (2017). (Sethi, G., Singh, & I.) Khan, I., & Iftikhar, F. (2017). The Impact of Email Marketing, Mobile Marketing and Retargeting on online Consumer Buying Behavior.
- Siamagka, N. T., Christodoulides, G., Michaelidou, N., & Valvi, A. (2015). Determinants of social media adoption by B2B organizations. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 51, 89-99.

- Singlegraincom. (2017, November 9). *Single Grain*. [Online]. Available from: <https://www.singlegrain.com/marketing-funnels/why-retargeting-is-absolutely-essential-for-any-marketing-funnel/>.
- Smith, K. T. (2011). Digital marketing strategies that Millennials find appealing, motivating, or just annoying. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 19(6), 489-499.
- Soebagyo, T. (2014). Analisa Pengaruh Store Image Terhadap Purchase Intention di Toserba “Ramai” Ngawi. *Journal Strategi Pemasaran*, 2(1), 9.
- Udeledu. (2017). [Online]. [10 November 2017]. Retrieved from Available from: <https://www1.udel.edu/alex/chapt6.html>.
- Yasmin, A., Tasneem, S., & Fatema, K. (2015). Effectiveness of Digital Marketing in the Challenging Age: An Empirical Study. *The International Journal of Management Science and Business Administration*, 1(5), 79-80.
- Zhu, F., & Zhang, X. (2010). Impact Of Online Consumer Reviews On Sales: The Moderating Role Of Product And Consumer Characteristics. *Journal of Marketing*, 74(2), 133-148.

APPENDIX- QUESTIONNAIRE

Please select (✓) the appropriate choice

Name: _____

Contact #: _____

Email ID: _____

Gender: Male Female

Age:

1. Less than 21
2. 21 to 30
2. 21 to 30
3. 31 to 40
4. 41 to 50
5. Above 50

Education:

- ★ Matriculation/O level
- ★ Intermediate/A level
- ★ Undergraduate
- ★ Graduate
- ★ Doctorate

Occupation:

1. Employee
2. Own Business
3. Student

Please select your desired response: For example: If your response is 4 (Agree) than it will be like this		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither nor	Agree	Strongly Agree
Consumer Buying Intention						
01	It is easy to choose and make comparison with other products while shopping online.	1	2	3	4	5
02	The website design helps me in searching the products easily	1	2	3	4	5
03	The website layout helps me in searching and selecting the right product while shopping online	1	2	3	4	5
04	I prefer to buy from website that provides me with quality of information	1	2	3	4	5
05	I feel safe and secure while shopping online	1	2	3	4	5
Social Media Marketing (SMM)						
01	Social Media innovates the ways of advertising products or services in an efficient manner	1	2	3	4	5
02	Social media outlets should be a brand utilize to engage with consumers.	1	2	3	4	5
03	People mostly buy which brand posts are most popular.	1	2	3	4	5
04	Consumers perceive information posted by the other consumers on brand's social media outlets to be trustworthy.	1	2	3	4	5
05	Social Media Marketing activities change the consumer's perception of a brand	1	2	3	4	5
Email Marketing						
01	You tend to purchase online via E-Mail marketing	1	2	3	4	5
02	E-Mail marketing contributes to enhance product awareness	1	2	3	4	5
03	You trust on that information which is sent to you via the E-Mail marketing	1	2	3	4	5
04	You think that information you receive via the E-Mail marketing is exciting and Attractive	1	2	3	4	5
05	E-Mail marketing has played an important role in changing your attitude toward products and services	1	2	3	4	5
Mobile Marketing						
01	Mobile ads are much better than other forms of Ads.	1	2	3	4	5
02	I feel mobile advertisement offers me timely information	1	2	3	4	5
03	I delete mobile advertisements immediately without reading it.	1	2	3	4	5
04	After viewing an ad on mobile phone, I would consider purchasing the product	1	2	3	4	5
05	I feel that getting useful information from mobile advertising saves time	1	2	3	4	5